

A Comparative Study of Jute and Cotton Celluloses.

By J. K. CHOWDHURY AND N. N. BASU.

The complex problem of the identity of celluloses from different sources has received attention from several investigators. Cross and Bevan and other investigators (Kruger, *Papier Fabr.*, 1925, 23, 767) believed that each variety of cellulose is different from the other and speak of celluloses and not of cellulose as a chemical unit. If this view be correct, each kind of cellulose would have a different chemical constitution and it would obviously be impossible to assign a definite chemical formula to cellulose.

Another school of investigators represented mainly by Heuser and his co-workers (Heuser and Haug, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1918, 31, 99; Heuser and Boedeker, *ibid.*, 1921, 34, 461; Heuser and Aiyer, *ibid.*, 1924, 37, 27) maintain that cellulose is a definite chemical entity. According to this view it would not only be possible to employ a general constitutional formula for all kinds of cellulose but it would also be possible to use cheaper varieties as raw material for the manufacture of different cellulose derivatives and for other cellulose industries. The question of the identity of celluloses is therefore important both from the theoretical and the industrial point of view.

The object of this investigation is to examine these two points of view, taking jute and cotton celluloses as a basis for comparison. For this purpose it is first necessary to prepare a standard cellulose from cotton and to purify jute cellulose in such a manner that it may approximate the standard cotton cellulose in its properties. The properties of the two standard celluloses can then be compared under identical conditions, special attention being given to the following:

- (1) Acetylation of the celluloses.
- (2) Yield of glucose. (a) As methylglucoside (Irvine and Hirst),
(b) as crystalline glucose (Monier Williams).
- (3) Yield of cellobiose octa-acetate.
- (4) Methylation of cellulose.
- (5) Characterisation of the cellulose by means of viscose reaction.

- (6) Surface tension of viscose solutions.
- (7) (a) Viscosity of the celluloses in cupra-ammonium solution,
(b) viscosity of cellulose acetates in chloroform,
(c) viscosity of the nitrocellulose in ether-alcohol solution.

Preparation of Standard Cellulose.

(a) *From Cotton.*—The methods of Schwalbe (*Chemie der Cellulose*, 1911, p. 602 and *Farb. Ztg.*, 1913, 436) Robinoff and the American Chemical Society—Cellulose Division (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 15, 748) recommend the use of a bleaching agent for the preparation of standard cellulose from cotton, but as it is difficult to prevent the action of bleaching agent on the cellulose itself the use of such chemicals has been avoided in this work and the method of Correy and Grey (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1924, 16, 852) has in general, been followed.

The alcohol-benzol extracted cotton was treated with a large volume of caustic soda solution (1%) with careful exclusion of air. The ash content was diminished by treatment with acetic acid. When the same procedure was applied to jute cellulose delignified by the chlorine peroxide method, it was found that the impurities could not be efficiently removed and the cellulose matter had to be subjected to the action of 17.5% cold alkali. In order to make the conditions comparative for cotton cellulose, the cellulose as prepared above from cotton was also subjected to the action of 17.5% alkali under the same conditions as for jute cellulose.

(b) *From Jute.*—Delignification of jute was effected by the chlorine peroxide method as previous experience in this laboratory (Chowdhury and Majumder, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 139) has shown that jute cellulose is little affected by this treatment. The delignified jute was then subjected to the action of 5% boiling alkali or 17.5% cold alkali. It was however found that neither method removed the hemicelluloses completely and that a part of the furfural-yielding complex remained in the residual cellulose, the minimum furfural value thus obtained being 2.5%. By a combination of the two processes, *i.e.* by alternate treatment for half an hour with cold concentrated alkali and boiling dilute alkali, the furfural value is reduced to 1.8%. Further reduction of the furfural value can be effected by continued previous extraction of the delignified fibre with boiling water, followed by alternate treatment with 17.5% cold alkali and 5% boiling alkali. By this treatment the furfural value is reduced to 0.25%

which compares very favourably with that of standard cotton cellulose as prepared by the above method. During the treatment with alkali, exposure to air was carefully avoided in order to prevent any consequent oxidation. The standard celluloses as obtained above were tested by means of its furfural value and their solubility in 17.5% cold alkali. The data in the following table represents the results obtained.

TABLE I.

Cotton cellulose.

Treatment.	Furfural.	Solubility in 17.5% cold alkali.
Raw cotton extracted with alcohol-benzol	1.8%	15.0%
Do treated once with 17.5% alkali	0.702	9.6
Do 5 times	0.31	2.5
Do and boiled twice with 5% alkali	0.29	1.9

TABLE II.

Jute cellulose: Treatments showing progressive reduction in furfural value and solubility in alkali.

Treatment.	Furfural.	Solubility in 17.5% alkali.
Delignified jute	9.6%	32.77%
Do treated once with 5% boiling alkali	3.4	22.58
Do treated 5 times	2.5	18.0
Do treated once with 17.5% cold alkali	2.5	18.45
Do treated 5 times	1.8	14.05
Delignified jute after 3 extractions with boiling water only	5.39	23.71
Do and then given one treatment with 17.5% cold alkali	1.02	10.08
Do and then given 4 successive similar treatments	0.31	1.85
Do further boiled twice with 5% alkali	0.25	1.82

TABLE III.

Analysis of the two purified celluloses.

	Jute.	Cotton.
Lignin	nil	nil
Furfural	0.25%	0.29%
Fats and resin	nil	nil
Ash	0.19%	0.1628%
Moisture	10.01%	8.3372%
Uronic acid	nil	nil
Solubility in 17.5% alkali	1.82%	1.9%

Acetylation.

It is well known that during acetylation the reagents and the temperature employed considerably affect the cellulose. We have therefore endeavoured to use a method of acetylation which would have the least possible action on cellulose itself. Only very few methods are available for such acetylation. As the methods represented in E.P. 297766 (1928) or that of Hess (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 461) require high temperature or a prolonged period for complete acetylation, the authors adopted the method of Barnett as modified by Irvine and Hirst (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1585). It was however found that this method if carried out at high temperature, as recommended by these authors, causes disintegration and partial decomposition of the product obtained from jute cellulose. If however the proportion of the reagents be slightly increased, it is possible to carry out the reaction at a much lower temperature when no such disadvantages are experienced and no reducing matter is found in the filtrate after precipitation of the acetate in water.

10 G of air-dried, finely shredded jute cellulose were placed in a stoppered bottle and incorporated with 65 c.c. of glacial acetic acid through which a stream of dry chlorine was passed for 40-50 seconds. After standing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, acetic anhydride (70 c.c.) was added and sulphur dioxide gas bubbled through the mixture for $1\frac{1}{2}$ minutes and the bottle stirred mechanically. After 3 to 4 hours, the cellulose gelatinised and began to dissolve slowly. Finally to hasten the reaction, the temperature was raised to 40°. The solution, when quite clear, was treated with chloroform and water in the manner recommended by Irvine and Hirst (*loc. cit.*). The whole procedure required some 35-40 hours. If however the

cellulose is previously dipped for about 1 hour in glacial acetic acid, pressed and dried in the air, the time of the reaction can be reduced to 20-24 hours. As this latter treatment might to some extent affect the cellulose, we have preferred not to use it during acetylation.

The acetyl content of the product was determined as follows : A weighed quantity of the acetate was boiled for 2 hours with a known excess of standard caustic soda solution, the excess of alkali being titrated with standard sulphuric acid. Owing to possible chemical action or the adsorption of caustic soda in the regenerated cellulose, each result was corrected by means of a control experiment in which pure cellulose was treated with caustic soda solution under the same conditions.

Some typical results are quoted :

(I) 0.4914 G. of jute acetate required 11.0032 c.c. of *N/2*- caustic soda while 0.5804 c.c. was used for control experiment. The percentage of acetyl therefore was 45.6.

(II) 0.8188 G. of jute acetate required 17.529 c.c. of *N/2*- caustic soda and the control experiment took 0.6214 c.c. The percentage of acetyl was 44.42.

(I) 0.4288 G. of cotton acetate took 9.9338 c.c. of *N/2*- alkali while 1.0684 c.c. were used for control experiment. The percentage was therefore 44.5.

(II) 0.4150 G. of cotton acetate took 9.6396 c.c. of *N/2*- alkali while the blank experiment required 1.0684 c.c. The percentage was therefore 44.4.

The detailed results obtained are given in the following table.

TABLE IV.

	Jute		Cotton	
	5	5	5	5
Cellulose (g.)	4.49	4.49	4.575	4.575
Water and ash-free cellulose (g.)	7.8921	7.9011	8.0823	8.1031
Acetate yield (g.)	175.8	176.0	176.0	177.2
Percentage of the yield	177.7	177.7	177.7	177.7
Theoretical value	44.42	45.6	44.4	44.5
Acetyl value	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8
Theoretical acetyl value				

Yield of Glucose.

As calculated from the yield of methylglucoside.—For the preparation of methylglucoside we have generally followed the

directions of Irvine and Hirst (*loc. cit.*) with slight modifications, having used a temperature of 135-40° instead of 125° and also a higher acid content (1.2%) in methyl alcohol in place of 0.75% recommended by them. With these modifications the time is reduced to 48 hours and the yield of glucosides is practically quantitative.

One part of acetate (nearly 4 g.) was treated in a sealed tube for 48 hours at 135-40° with methyl alcohol (15 parts) containing 1.2% hydrochloric acid. At the end of this period only a slight trace of solid remained undissolved in case of both jute and cotton celluloses and the liquid had assumed a faint golden yellow colour. The contents of the tube were then filtered, carefully neutralised with silver carbonate and decolourised with animal charcoal. Precautions were taken to recover any matter adhering to the filter paper and to the charcoal residues. Finally it was concentrated under reduced pressure (10 mm.) and left overnight in a calcium chloride desiccator, when it set to a solid mass. The last trace of solvent was driven away by means of hot dry air.

Finally it was dried in vacuum over calcium chloride to constant weight. We have here eliminated the distillation of the solvent under reduced pressure recommended by the above authors and thus avoided a tiresome process and the mechanical loss involved in it. The crystals melted between 125-48° and gave 15.92% methoxyl in case of glucoside from jute and 15.925% in case of glucoside from cotton. No mineral matter was present and no furfural was liberated on treatment with 12% hydrochloric acid (boiling). Details of two typical experiments are recorded for each particular cellulose.

TABLE V.

	Jute		Cotton	
Wt. of acetate (dry and ash-free) (g.)	3.8	3.779	3.805	3.892
Acid methyl alcohol used (1.2% HCl.) (c.c.)	60	60	60	60
Time (135-40°) (hr.)	48	48	48	48
Wt. of solid remaining in the sealed tubes (g.)	nil	0.082	nil	0.05
Permanent sp. rotation [α] _D ²⁵	106°	106°	107°	106°
Yield of dry crystals	2.56	2.49	2.549	2.6334
Yield (%)	99.492	93.458	98.925	97.37
Methoxyl (%)	15.92	—	15.925	—
Equiv. glucose (%)	99.98	99.952	99.413	97.858

It will be observed from the above data that the yield from both cases is quantitative and is thus an improvement on 95.5% obtained by Irvine and Hirst. In calculating the yield, the weight of insoluble matter left in the tube after the reaction was deducted from the weight of cellulose taken. The melting point of the mixed glucosides varied from 125—143° according to the proportion of β -glucoside present. The purity of the methylglucoside was established by hydrolysis of the glucosides with 4% hydrochloric acid and noting the specific rotation of the glucose formed.

2.2614 G. of methylglucoside from jute cellulose were boiled under reflux with 25 c.c. of 4% hydrochloric acid solution for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the contents of the flask were then carefully made up to 100 c.c. The specific rotation obtained was $[\alpha]_D^{29} = 52.25^\circ$ ($\alpha = 1.096$, $l = 1$ dm., $c = 2.0982$), the corresponding figure for pure glucose being 52.5° .

A similar procedure was adopted in case of methylglucoside from cotton and the specific rotation was found to be $[\alpha]_D^{28.5} = 52.2^\circ$, showing thereby that both the glucosides are made up entirely of glucose residues.

That the methylglucosides from both jute and cotton consist only of glucose was further established indirectly in the following manner:

On recrystallisation of the mixed glucosides from absolute alcohol characteristic crystals of m.p. 165° and $[\alpha]_D^{29} = 157.6^\circ$ (in aqueous solution) were obtained ($\alpha = 1.84$, $l = 1$ dm., $c = 1.17$), the corresponding figure for α -methylglucosides being 165–166° and 157.5° respectively. The mother liquor after separation of the crystals of α -methylglucosides evidently contained a larger proportion of β -form. On heating this mother liquor again with 1.2% acid methyl alcohol for 48 hours in sealed tubes, the equilibrium between α - and β -forms was re-established and the specific rotation was found to be $[\alpha]_D^{28} = 106^\circ$. Evidently no other sugars except glucose are present in the mixed glucosides. As the theoretical yield of methylglucosides has been obtained both from the jute and cotton celluloses, it follows that both the celluloses are made up entirely of glucose, and no other hexose or pentose constitute an essential part in the molecules of the celluloses.

Hydrolysis with sulphuric acid.—Attempts were then made to ascertain the maximum yield of glucose obtained by the hydrolysis of the two celluloses under identical conditions. For this purpose the well known method of Monier Williams was followed in preference to the method of Keisel and Semiganoski (*Trans. Chem.*

Pharm. Inst. Moscow, 1927, 18, 82) who claim 100% yield of glucose from cotton cellulose, as they did not isolate the sugar in crystalline form.

5 G. of the cellulose were dissolved in 30 c.c. of 72 % sulphuric acid and the dark coloured viscous solution was allowed to remain 1 week at room temperature. The sulphuric acid solution was diluted to 3 litres with water and boiled continuously under reflux for 15 hours. A small amount of dark coloured flocculent precipitate was found in the liquid. This was filtered off, dried and deducted from the weight of the cellulose used. After boiling, the almost colourless liquid was neutralised with barium hydroxide, filtered clear from the sulphate and evaporated to dryness by distilling at a low temperature under reduced pressure (10 mm.). A slight alkalinity developed during evaporation which was always made neutral by means of *N*/10-sulphuric acid. The residue from the distillation was extracted with pure methyl alcohol, filtered and decolorised with animal charcoal. The solution was then concentrated under reduced pressure but it was very difficult to crystallise the syrup even after passing hot dry air through the mass. Crystallisation however took place on the addition of a very small amount of pure glucose. From this crude product glucose was purified by recrystallisation from absolute alcohol and was tested by means of its melting point and that of its osazone. For the sake of comparison, the data are represented below :

TABLE VI.

	Jute		Cotton	
	5	5	5	5
Wt. of cellulose (g.)				
Wt. of ash-free dry cellulose (g.)	4.49	4.49	4.575	4.575
Wt. of glucose obtained (g.)	4.7055	4.6336	4.8952	4.6812
Yield (%)	104.8	103.2	107.0	105.6
Theoretical value (%)	111.1	111.1	111.1	111.1
M.p. of glucose	145°	146°	144°	145°
M.p. of the osazone	204°	205°	205°	205.5°

Yield of Cellobiose Octa-acetate.

The yield of cellobiose octa-acetate from both jute and cotton was next ascertained, as this question has an important significance in regard to the constitution of cellulose.

The highest yield of cellobiose octa-acetate found from cellulose material is 50% obtained by Hess and Frieze (*Annalen*, 1927, 466, 38), but as this process is tedious and as other investigators have not been able to obtain the same high yield by following their directions, we preferred to follow the method of Spenser (*Cellulosechem.*, 1929, 10, 61) who obtained a maximum yield of 46.5%. The best yield was obtained at 50° with 0.2 c.c. of sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) after a period of 15 days, the maximum yield of cellobiose octa-acetate from jute being 41.14% while that from cotton was 43.8%.

8 C.c. of acetic anhydride were taken in a stoppered conical flask and cooled to 0° and 0.6 c.c., 0.4 c.c., 0.2 c.c. of sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) was cautiously added in three different cases without causing any appreciable rise of temperature. 2 G. of jute and cotton celluloses were separately added to the reagent mixture, which was then cooled for 30 minutes and kept at room temperature until the maximum yield was obtained. The product was recrystallised from alcohol and showed the characteristic reactions of cellobiose octa-acetate. Under the microscope, a drop of the hot solution gave characteristic rosettes of needles. Both the samples melted at 226° and 227° and gave the specific rotation $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 41.5^\circ$ and 41.6° respectively in chloroform solution.

TABLE VII.

Yield of cellobiose octa-acetate.

Cellulose used.	Temp.	Sulphuric acid (<i>d</i> 1.84).	Days.	Maximum yield.
Jute	39.5-40°	0.2 c. c.	25	15.4%
Cotton	"	"	25	22.3
Jute	"	0.4	25	35.1
Cotton	"	"	25	35.1
Jute	"	0.6	15	29.3
Cotton	"	"	15	28.3
Jute	50°	0.2	15	41.14
Cotton	"	"	"	43.8

Although the mechanism of acetolysis of celluloses is not clearly understood and the period of reaction is comparatively long, the agreement in the maximum yield of cellobiose octa-acetate is quite satisfactory and points to the identity of two celluloses from the chemical point of view.

Methylation of Cellulose.

Attention was then directed to the maximum methoxyl content in the methylcellulose from jute. In the preliminary experiments, the tedious method of Denham and Woodhouse (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 77) with the modification of Irvine and Hirst (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 528) for the methylation of cellulose was followed, but the maximum yield of methoxyl obtained in case of jute after thirteen repeated alkylations was only 32.5% and this value could not be appreciably increased even after seventeen methylations. As this value is considerably lower than the theoretical maximum (45.5%), we followed Urban's method (*Cellulosechem.*, 1926, 7, 73) for the methylation of lignin from spruce wood. The method applied to jute cellulose gave very satisfactory results and a methoxyl content of 44.3% was obtained after 10 operations, a value which could not be substantially increased after repeating the process 15 times (theoretical, 45.5%). It may be noted here that the maximum methoxyl value obtained by Irvine and Hirst (*loc. cit.*) in the case of cotton cellulose was 43.1 to 44.5%.

5 G. of finely shredded jute cellulose were dipped in 150 c. c. of 45% caustic potash solution in a stoppered bottle and shaken vigorously in a shaking machine for 6 hours. It was then cooled with ice and salt and dimethyl sulphate (5 c. c. at a time) was added at intervals of $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The procedure was continued with occasional shaking until the mixture was acidic. It was then washed well first with distilled water and then with alcohol and ether and dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid.

This method has the advantage over that of Irvine and Hirst (*loc. cit.*) that in this case no ethereal solution of dimethyl sulphate is required. The process is conducted at a lower temperature with less dimethyl sulphate and with less fear of disintegration of the product. The use of alcoholic alkali accompanied by a sudden rise of temperature is avoided.

*Differentiation of the two Celluloses by means of the
Viscose Reaction.*

Lieser (*Cellulosechem.*, 1929, 10, 21) has been able to characterise different celluloses by means of the above reaction. He has shown that the cellulose-A, which is soluble in alkali, requires a minimum concentration of only 7.5% caustic soda to form alkali cellulose and undergo subsequent reaction with carbon disulphide to form viscose, while cotton cellulose requires a minimum concentration

of 16 % caustic soda for the above purpose, intermediate concentrations being necessary for other types of celluloses.

In the following experiments the concentration of alkali was varied from 10% to 17.5% in order to ascertain the minimum strength necessary for mercerisation of each of the two celluloses which would then react with carbon disulphide to form viscose.

It was found that a different strength of alkali was necessary in each case and that for the same strength of alkali, the residue obtained after the formation of viscose was always greater in the case of cotton than that in the case of jute. This may be attributed to the greater resisting power of cotton, due mainly to physical difference in composition and arrangements of the micels. The solubility, viscosity, the time required for coagulation of viscose solutions prepared from the two celluloses were, however, widely different.

For the preparation of viscose we have used the following two methods:

(A) 1 G. of the cellulose was dipped in 20 c. c. of alkali for 3 days, the excess of the alkali pressed out, carbon disulphide added and the mixture agitated in a shaking machine for a few hours. The reaction product was then dissolved in 5 % alkali, 10 c. c. being added every $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solution was made upto 100 c.c. and filtered in a tared gooch crucible through fine muslin.

(B) 1 G. of cellulose was dipped first in carbon disulphide for 1 hour, the excess poured off and 20 c.c. of alkali of desired strength were added and shaken for 1 hour. It was then made upto 100 c.c. with 5% solution of caustic soda in the usual manner. The results obtained are given in the following table.

TABLE VIII.

Properties of viscose prepared by the methods (A) and (B).

Fibre.	Alkali conc.	Residue (g.).		Viscosity sec. (Ostwald).		Coagulation days.	
		A	B	A	B	A	B
Jute	15% NaOH	nil	nil	20'43"	28'25"	5	7
Cotton	"	0.1812	0.052	35'7"	58' 2"	2	3
Jute	12% "	0.208	nil	3'12"	4'39"	27 hr.	39hr.
Cotton	"	0.602	0.442	5'24"	12'33"	24 hr.	24hr.
Jute	10% "	0.639	0.212	43"	68"	36 "	24 "
Cotton	"	0.87	0.85	76"	98"	24 "	24 "

*Surface Tension of the Viscoscs prepared from Jute and
Cotton Celluloses.*

As it was suspected that the variation in physical properties e.g., viscosity, solubility, coagulation, etc., of the above viscose solutions might be due to the character and size of the micellae composing the two celluloses, it was thought advisable to test the surface tension of the two solutions. It is known that the surface tension diminishes with the thickness of films formed at the surface of a solution at different intervals. As the formation of such films is due to collection of micellae, it was thought likely that the surface tension would diminish as the micellae accumulate at the surface. The method used for determination of the surface tension is that developed by Ghosh and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 103) in this laboratory who observed similar changes in surface tension of solutions of different dyestuffs and attributed to the formation of micellae.

The experimental details are the same as those of the above authors. The viscose used for this purpose was prepared from the two celluloses by the method (B) previously described using 17.5% alkali, the solution obtained from 1g. of cellulose being made upto 500 c.c. with distilled water. The variation of the surface tension with time was then noted, surface tension being calculated as follows:—

$$\text{Surface tension of the solution} = \frac{\sigma W_2}{W_1}$$

where σ is the surface tension of water at the temperature of the experiment, W_2 is the weight required to raise the basin from the surface of the solution, and W_1 is the weight required to raise the basin from the surface of water.

As coagulation took place after some time (which may be attributed to increase in the size and number of micellae), we could not observe the minimum surface tension. Our object was however attained by the character of the curve obtained in the two cases. The results obtained are noted in Table IX and are further brought out in the plotted curve on the next page.

FIG. 1.

TABLE IX.

*Surface tension of viscose solutions made from jute.*Temp. = 29.2°. $\sigma = 71.18$. $W_1 = 2.108$.

Time (min.)	...	0	20	42	61	85	110
W_1	...	1.48	1.3	1.2	1.18	1.179	1.178
Surface tension of viscose	...	49.98	42.89	40.52	39.85	39.81	39.71

TABLE X.

*Surface tension of viscose solutions made from cotton.*Temp. = 29.2°. $\sigma = 71.18$. $W_1 = 2.108$.

Time (min.)	...	0	14	40	70
W_2	...	1.203	1.125	1.117	1.111
Surface tension of viscose	...	40.62	38.48	37.70	37.52

Particular attention may be drawn to the higher surface tension of jute viscose. This phenomenon may be attributed to the smaller size of micellae or to a smaller molecular weight of the molecules composing jute fibre owing to the smaller degree of polymerisation of glucose units. The two curves are, however, similar in character which indicates similar changes taking place in the viscose solutions on standing and suggests a similarity in chemical constitution.

It may be noted that viscose made from cotton cellulose coagulates in a shorter time than jute viscose in which the particles or micellae in colloidal solution are evidently smaller in size.

Viscosity Tests.

Cupra-ammonium solution.—(a) The cupra-ammonium solution was made according to the directions of Hibbert and Parson (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, **44**, 483π). Cupric hydroxide was first prepared by cautiously adding slight excess of ammonium hydroxide to a concentrated filtered solution of boiling copper sulphate solution. The precipitate was allowed to settle, washed by decantation with hot water, cooled below 10° by the addition of a few lumps of ice, and

then sufficient 9% caustic soda was slowly introduced with stirring until the deep blue colour of copper hydroxide was formed. The precipitate was then filtered, washed free from alkali with cold water and then with alcohol and water. It was dried in the air for several days and passed through a 40-mesh sieve.

4 G. of an air-dried sample of cellulose were introduced into a stoppered bottle along with 4 g. of copper hydroxide as prepared above, 225 c.c. of a 28% ammonium hydroxide solution were then added, the bottle stoppered and the mixture shaken mechanically. Viscosity was measured by means of the Ostwald apparatus. It was found that the viscosity of the solution obtained from jute was lower (8' 28" at 29°) than that from cotton (10' 24" at the same temperature).

(b) The same result was obtained by observing the viscosity of cellulose acetate in chloroform. A 6.4% cellulose acetate solution in chloroform was found to have a viscosity of 3' 35" at 29.5° in the case of jute and 28' 52" at the same temperature in the case of cotton.

(c) 1% Solution of nitrocellulose in ether-alcohol (55:45) gave a viscosity (at 20°) of 4" in the case of cotton and 0.5" in the case of jute, when determined by the falling sphere viscometer of Gibson and Jacobs.

Solubility tests.—While preparing the cupra-ammonium solution as described above, it was found that cotton cellulose required 1½ hours for complete solution while jute cellulose dissolved in ½ hour. In the case of cellulose acetate it was found that the product obtained from cotton was not easily soluble in chloroform, a 6.4% solution being obtained with some difficulty while the acetate obtained from jute cellulose under identical conditions was easily soluble. The same remarks are applicable to nitrocelluloses prepared from jute and cotton, the former being easily soluble in alcohol-ether and in acetone while nitrocellulose prepared under identical conditions from cotton was soluble with difficulty.

It may be noted here that the lower viscosity and higher solubility of different derivatives obtained from jute cellulose are interesting also from certain industrial points of view, as several industries, particularly the lacquer industry, prefer cellulose derivatives of low viscosity and high solubility in order that coating compositions may be prepared with maximum content of cellulose acetate or cellulose nitrate.

Summary and Conclusions.

It will be evident from the experiments described above that chemical tests indicate the identity of jute and cotton celluloses. Thus, practically the same yield of cellulose acetate is obtained in both cases, the yield of glucose as determined by the yield of methylglucoside is practically quantitative and the yield of crystalline glucose is almost identical in both instances. The same observation is true of the yield of cellulose octa-acetate and the percentage of methoxyl in methylated cellulose. It may, however, be observed that there is a slight difference in the behaviour of the two celluloses when tested by means of alkali of different concentrations with the subsequent formation of viscose. The difference is, however, more prominent in the case of physical tests *e. g.*, surface tension, viscosity, solubility and the time of coagulation of viscose solutions. These differences are not without significance on the constitution of cellulose.

Cellulose is usually represented by the formula $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$, 'n' being unknown. The usual assumption that 'n' is a very great number is contradicted by recent works of Pringsheim (*Annalen*, 1926, **448**, 163), Karrer (*Cellulosechem.*, 1921, **2**, 127), Hess and co-workers (*Annalen*, 1926, **448**, 104), Irvine and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 518) as well as by the röntgenographic investigations of Herzog and others, which point to the probability of 'n' being a very small figure lying between 1 and 4. On the other hand the investigations of Staudinger and his co-workers (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, **126**, 425) as well as of Meyer and Mark (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 1103) make it highly probable that cellulose is formed by the polymerisation of the glucose unit and that the degree of polymerisation is probably very high and may differ in different cases.

According to these latter investigators some 30-35 glucose molecules are linked with one another by means of the main valency along the axis of the fibre in the form of a chain while some 40-60 chains are linked side by side by means of the secondary valency of hydroxyl groups to form a micell, several of these micellae forming the cell of the fibre.

The results obtained in the foregoing experiments give support to the latter view. It appears highly probable that the degree of polymerisation (or at least the size of the micellae) is different in different cases. The degree of polymerisation in the case of jute

cellulose is evidently lower than in the case of cotton. This would explain the higher surface tension, lower viscosity and greater solubility in the case of jute cellulose derivatives.

Though it is evident from the above investigations that purified cellulose from jute and that from cotton give identical results from the chemical point of view, it would be premature to say at this stage that they are identical in all respects. Both jute and cotton celluloses consist of poly-anhydroglucose residues, each glucose unit being probably linked to another in exactly the same manner. But the number of glucose residues constituting a poly-anhydroglucose unit appears to be different in the two cases.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

Received November 5, 1952.

